

Calculating the Effectiveness of RCNN-based Coral Reef Classification

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ABSTRACT

In a prior study (Gunti & Rorissa, 2021), the coral reef classification system (Krizhevsky, Sutskever, & Hinton, 2017) encountered a massive overlap between predictions and resulted in lower precision and recall scores after submission at the Annotation and Localisation Challenge (*AIcrowd | ImageCLEF Coral - Annotation and Localisation | Challenges, 2022*). This current study investigates the overlapping issue to improve system performance and classifies the limited number of coral substrates using the Image Conference and Labs Evaluation Forums (CLEF) coral dataset (*ImageCLEFcoral | ImageCLEF / LifeCLEF - Multimedia Retrieval in CLEF, 2021-22*). The testing and evaluation were performed on the manually annotated dataset (*ImageCLEFcoral | ImageCLEF / LifeCLEF - Multimedia Retrieval in CLEF, 2021-22*). To improve performance, we set up the open-source object-detection system (Yu et al., 2020) and used faster Region-Based Convolutional Neural Network (RCNN) TensorFlow models (open-source Machine Learning software library) to test the developed python script and evaluate the CLEF test Image Dataset (CoralClef) (*ImageCLEFcoral | ImageCLEF / LifeCLEF - Multimedia Retrieval in CLEF, 2021-22*) predictions. Our findings could assist in the refinement of the increased CNN-based retrieval systems using different models' results to develop it more efficiently for future LifeCLEF and Mediaeval Tasks. Additionally, the study's findings impact video retrieval, sport detection, and interview response filtering with wider significance for relevant fields.

KEYWORDS

Image Classification, TensorFlow Models, Convolution Neural Network, Precision, chi-square & Mean, Annotation, and Localisation.

INTRODUCTION

In our prior studies (Gunti & Rorissa, 2021; Gunti & Rorissa, 2022), the training and testing of the coral reefs were performed on different platforms like MATLAB and Anaconda Python using different programming languages to test the effectiveness of the open-source system that can be further developed into a compatible application for retrieval tasks. Therefore, to find the efficacy of the system, entering the competition (*AIcrowd | ImageCLEF Coral - Annotation and Localisation | Challenges, 2021-22*) for two consecutive years to calculate the Precision and Recall values proved to be fruitful because improved classification was observed and the TensorFlow open-source software library to be more promising (Gunti & Rorissa, 2022). In prior studies (Gunti & Rorissa, 2021; Gunti & Rorissa, 2022), although we achieved improved training scores, they were considerably low and ranged around 0.003 in accuracy and 0.002 in recall. Upon further inspection, we observed that the annotations used from the training Dataset (*AIcrowd | ImageCLEF Coral - Annotation and Localisation | Challenges, 2022*) had measurements in width,height, x minimum (xmin) on x axis, and y minimum value (ymin) on y axis. These were different from the trained annotation format x minimum, y minimum, xmax (width), and ymax (height) that were used in the 2021 challenge (*AIcrowd | ImageCLEF Coral - Annotation and Localisation | Challenges, 2021-22*). The misplacement of the coordinated CSV file while training caused overlapping and low accuracy, as demonstrated in the results for one of our previous studies (Gunti & Rorissa, 2022). To resolve this overlapping issue, the system was trained by creating manual annotations and testing. Hence, this resulted in a better-refined system's accuracy and a compatible image retrieval system for future studies and other retrieval tasks using different forms of data like Text/Literature classification (Agarwal, 2015), Audio (Piczak, K. J, 2015), and Video (Wang, 2011). In support of that, we have observed a growing need among a communication and information science research cohort at the college of communication and information, University of Tennessee, Knoxville (CCI) (*College of Communication & Information - University of Tennessee, 2023*) that identified similar retrieval applications that would be relevant to various CCI schools and groups, such as:

- Sports Journalism: A video retrieval system that can identify the type of sports or sport activity.
- Advertising and Public relations: A text retrieval system detecting the validity of social media data (Twitter or Facebook) by evaluating the words/Identifying consumer effective responses on social media using data from twitter.
- Communication Studies: Filtering participant audio responses from a different interview recordings in various qualitative research studies like student experiences in COVID-19 Pandemic.

The findings have implications for the development of video retrieval systems for social media data analysis, sport detection, and Interview audio response filter which could be of interest to professionals in these fields. Therefore, it can be argued that the study has wider significance and potential relevance beyond its specific focus in retrieval.

DATA

The datasets used for this study were Image related conferences and labs such as the ImageCLEF evaluation forum and its Annotation and Localization tasks. The datasets consist of images (JPG) of coral reefs collected from around the world through the Marine Technology Research Unit at the University of Essex. The datasets were created using both training and testing datasets, selecting a total of 1340 images partitioned into 1200 training images (90%) and 140 testing Images (10%). The dataset consists of a good blend of images from several islands in the data collection area. The annotations were created manually using an open-source annotation tool named “labelImg” on Anaconda 5.1.1 with the Python 3.7 programming language.

Methodology

The classification method we used is the same as in the previous study, although the model configuration and training patterns differ. Annotating the images manually on LabelImg gave considerate results in the end. To keep it simple and convenient to evaluate, seven substrates were trained with around 775 annotations considering 100 per each coral class. The seven coral classes include three Hard Corals (Branching, Mushroom and Boulder), two soft corals (Soft Coral and Gorgonian), and Sponge and Sponge Barrel. Table 1 below shows the coral class trained and overall accuracy using the TensorFlow (v1.13.1, v1.14.0 and v1.15.0) RCNN Object detection model with `ssd_mobilenet_v1_pets` configuration on Anaconda 5.1.0 CMD prompt and Anaconda 5.3.3 command prompt– To train. A five-step method (Gunti & Rorissa, 2021) was used to process and conduct the classification of an image using TensorFlow models:

- **Image Acquisition:** Capturing the input image from the source file using the “GET” function. However, if the image has not been acquired satisfactorily, the intended tasks may not be achievable, even with some form of image enhancement.
- **Image Resizing or Scaling:** A process that involves a trade-off between efficiency, smoothness, and sharpness.
- **Image Segmentation:** The process of partitioning an image into multiple segments (set of pixels or superpixels). The goal is to represent the image as something more meaningful and assign a label to every pixel in an image so that pixels with the same label share specific characteristics.
- **Feature Extraction:** A convolutional layer condenses the input by extracting features of interest and producing feature maps responding to different feature detectors.
- **Classification:** This is the top layer of a network that collects the final convoluted feature and returns a column vector where each row points towards a class.

Finally, a four-way Crosstab Chi-Square Statistic and Skewness were calculated using Statistical package for social science (SPSS) – a relatively new approach to validate the computed classification scores.

RESULTS

Substrate : Hard Coral Boulder Number of Annotations trained: 101 Detections: 6 Accuracy : 56%	
Substrate : Hard Coral Branching Number of Annotations trained: 110 Detections: 11 Accuracy : 62%	
Substrate : Hard Coral Mushroom Number of Annotations trained: 135 Detections: 7 Accuracy : 83%	

Substrate : Soft Coral Number of Annotations trained: 125 Detections: 11 Accuracy : 62%	
Substrate : Soft Coral Gorgonian Number of Annotations trained: 100 Detections: 6 Accuracy : 90%	
Substrate: Sponge Coral Number of Annotations trained: 101 Detections: 2 Accuracy : 78%	
Substrate: Sponge Coral Barrel Number of Annotations trained: 103 Detections: 4 Accuracy : 62%	

Table 1. Below are the classified corals and their performance metrics from the test dataset(Arorissa/Asis-TMYC: GitHub, Dataset, 2022).

The classification results were auspicious to continue working on the TensorFlow Model Garden and TensorFlow Model Zoo configurations to develop future retrieval systems that meet the growing needs of image classification researchers. Compared to the results in prior studies, this study met the classification targets by overcoming the previous challenges. Figures 1 & 2 show a comparison of the results. In Figure 1, the result on the left side is the overlapped classification of an output image from CLEF 2022 due to misplaced annotations. The right side shows the output for the current study that localizes the image with two soft coral classifications of fifty-eight percent accuracy on the left and fifty-nine percent on the right.

Figure 1. Comparison of classification results from previous (left) and current (right) studies 1.

Figure 2. Comparison of classification results from previous (left) and current (right) studies 2.

Figure 2, similar to Figure 1, shows comparative results from the previous and current studies. In Figure 2, the left side depicts the overlapped classification of an output image from CLEF 2022 due to misplaced annotations. The right side is the output for the current study that localizes the image with two mushrooms (70% and 50% Accuracy) and branching (96% accuracy) classifications.

Figure 3. The skewness of coral image detection data (left) and accuracy of classification (right).

The results presented in Figure 3 show the fact that coral image detection data is positively skewed (left graph), while the figure on the right reflects the considerable accuracy of most of the classifications of coral images. Some corals, like Sponge and Barrel, did not classify (High classification Loss/Localization Loss and low Precision and Recall Score) as anticipated. However, training and testing with other models with the required configuration will help improve classification performance.

Chi-Square Tests				Symmetric Measures				
Anotations_greater_than_100		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Anotations_greater_than_100		Value	Approximate Significance
yes	Pearson Chi-Square	47.000*	6	<.001	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1.000	<.001
	Likelihood Ratio	35.900	6	<.001		Cramer's V		1.000
	Linear-by-Linear Association	22.843	1	<.001	N of Valid Cases		47	
	N of Valid Cases	47						
Total	Pearson Chi-Square	47.000*	6	<.001	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1.000	<.001
	Likelihood Ratio	35.900	6	<.001		Cramer's V		1.000
	Linear-by-Linear Association	22.843	1	<.001	N of Valid Cases		47	
	N of Valid Cases	47						

a. 9 cells (64.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .26.

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Evaluation result = $\chi^2(1, 47) = 47.00, p < 0.05$

Where O_i = observed detections

E_i = expected number of detection

$E_i = N/k$, where k is the number of coral substrates

Figure 4. Results of a chi-square test of the relationship between the number of detections and coral categories.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

While our previous study (Gunti and Rorissa, 2021) resulted in overlaps between predictions with lower precision and recall scores, the current study corrected the overlapping issue and improved system performance and classification results. To improve system performance, among other things, we used faster Region-Based Convolutional Neural Network (RCNN) TensorFlow models to test a python script and evaluate test Image Datasets obtained through the ImageCLEFcoral evaluation campaign. For future studies, we would be testing different models (Welcome to the Model Garden for TensorFlow, 2016/2022) with different configurations (Tensorflow/Models, 2022) and developing python scripts for further multimedia retrieval tasks. The current study and evaluation served a validating role. However, for future works, we will:

- Divide the training dataset of 1200 images into two parts of training and validation to test the original test dataset for the final performance. This would be a considerable approach as suggested by one of the ASIS&T MidYear Conference 2023 reviewers.
- Partition of the filenames, duplicating the images, and increasing folders' sizes as performed in our prior study (Gunti & Rorissa, 2022). Using this study's refined system and tool (SPSS) for validation could be another considerable future implication.

Finally, the observations from the studies will be used for future challenges and in retrieval activities for training, testing, and validation. Our findings could assist in the refinement of the increased CNN-based retrieval systems using different models' results to develop it more efficiently for future Life CLEF and Mediaeval Tasks. Additionally, the study's finding could impact video retrieval, sport detection, and interview response filtering with wider significance for relevant fields.

REFERENCES

- 2023 Mid-Year Conference—Association for Information Science and Technology / ASIS&T %. (n.d.). Retrieved March 11, 2023, from <https://www.asist.org/my23/>
- Agarwal, S., & Singh, S. (2015). A comparative analysis of classification techniques for text classification. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 119(18), 26-29. <https://doi.org/10.5120/21126-7088>
- AIcrowd | ImageCLEF 2021 Coral—Annotation and Localisation | Insights. (n.d.). Retrieved October 20, 2022, from <https://www.aicrowd.com/challenges/imageclef-2021-coral-annotation-and-localisation/insights>
- AIcrowd | ImageCLEF 2022 Coral—Annotation and Localisation | Challenges. (n.d.). Retrieved October 13, 2022, from <https://www.aicrowd.com/challenges/imageclef-2022-coral-annotation-and-localisation>
- Anaconda | Anaconda Distribution. (n.d.). Retrieved October 21, 2022, from <https://www.anaconda.com/products/distribution>
- Yu, H., Chen, C., Du, X., Li, Y., Rashwan, A., Hou, L., Jin, P., Yang, F., Liu, F., Kim, J., & Li, J. (2020). TensorFlow Model Garden [Python]. <https://github.com/tensorflow/models>
- Arorissa/Asis-TMYC: Dataset. (n.d.). Retrieved March 12, 2023, from <https://github.com/arorissa/Asis-TMYC>
- Classification: Precision and Recall | Machine Learning. (n.d.). Google Developers. Retrieved November 2, 2022, from <https://developers.google.com/machine-learning/crash-course/classification/precision-and-recall>
- College of Communication & Information—University of Tennessee. (n.d.). Retrieved October 21, 2022, from <https://cci.utk.edu/>
- Gajjar, A. H., Raghuwanshi, S. S., & Singh, S. K. (2020). Coral reef classification using deep convolutional neural network. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 58(3), 1777-1787. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2019.2959478.
- Gunti, R.R., & Rorissa, A. (2021). A Convolutional Neural Networks based Coral Reef Annotation and Localization. Conference and Labs of the Evaluation Forum. Retrieved from <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2936/paper-100.pdf>.
- Gunti, R., & Rorissa, A. (2022). A Dual Convolutional Neural Networks and regression model based Coral Reef Annotation and Localization. CLEF 2022 Working Notes, 1396–1412.
- Heartexlabs/labelImg: LabelImg is now part of the Label Studio community. The popular image annotation tool created by Tzutalin is no longer actively being developed, but you can check out Label Studio, the open source data labeling tool for images, text, hypertext, audio, video and time-series data. (n.d.). Retrieved October 20, 2022, from <https://github.com/heartexlabs/labelImg>
- ImageCLEFcoral | ImageCLEF / LifeCLEF - Multimedia Retrieval in CLEF. (n.d.-a). Retrieved October 13, 2022, from <https://www.imageclef.org/2022/coral>
- ImageCLEFcoral | ImageCLEF / LifeCLEF - Multimedia Retrieval in CLEF. (n.d.-b). Retrieved October 20, 2022, from <https://www.imageclef.org/2021/coral>
- Kahl, S., Denton, T., Klinck, H., Glotin, H., Goëau, H., Vellinga, W.-P., Planqué, R., & Joly, A. (2021). Overview of BirdCLEF 2021: Bird call identification in soundscape recordings. CEUR-WS.Org, 2936, 1437--1450.
- Krizhevsky, A., Sutskever, I., & Hinton, G. E. (2017). ImageNet classification with deep convolutional neural networks. *Communications of the ACM*, 60(6), 84-90. doi: 10.1145/3065386
- LifeCLEF 2023 | ImageCLEF / LifeCLEF - Multimedia Retrieval in CLEF. (n.d.). Retrieved October 13, 2022, from <https://www.imageclef.org/node/297>
- Lorieul, T., Cole, E., Deneu, B., Servajean, M., & Bonnet, P. (2021). Overview of GeoLifeCLEF 2021: Predicting species distribution from 2 million remote sensing images. CLEF 2021 - Conference and Labs of the Evaluation Forum, 2936, 1451–1462.
- Martin, P.-E., Calandre, J., Mansencal, B., Benois-Pineau, J., Péteri, R., Mascarilla, L., & Morlier, J. (2021). Sports Video: Fine-Grained Action Detection and Classification of Table Tennis Strokes from Videos for MediaEval 2021. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2112.11384>
- Models/tf2_detection_zoo.md at master · tensorflow/models. (n.d.). Retrieved October 21, 2022, from https://github.com/tensorflow/models/blob/master/research/object_detection/g3doc/tf2_detection_zoo.md
- Piczak, K. J. (2015). Environmental sound classification with convolutional neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 24(11), 2079-2093. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TASLP.2016.2560244>
- Predicting Video Memorability. (2022, October 4). MediaEval Benchmark. <https://multimediaeval.github.io/editions/2022/tasks/memorability/>

Wang, H., Kläser, A., Schmid, C., & Liu, C.-L. (2011). Action recognition by dense trajectories. Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 3169-3176.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2011.5995406>